

INFLUENCE OF YOGIC PRACTICES ON SELECTED PHYSIOLOGICAL VARIABLES AMONG COLLEGE WOMEN

Aji P L

Assistant Professor, Government Sanskrit College, Thiruvananthapuram, Kerala

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Abstract:

The purpose of the study was to find out the effect of yogic practices on selected physiological variables among college women. To achieve the purpose of this study thirty women were randomly selected from Government Sanskrit College, Thiruvananthapuram. The subject's age ranged between 18 to 21 years only. The subjects (N=30) were randomly assigned to two equal groups of fifteen students. The groups were assigned as experimental group, and control group respectively. Pretest was conducted for all the subjects on selected physiological variables. The experimental group participated yogic practices for a period of six weeks. The post test was conducted on the above said dependent variables after a period of six weeks in the respective treatments. The analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was used to find out the effects of yogic practices on selected physiological variables among college women. It was concluded that there was significant improvement in slow vital capacity and forced vital capacity due to yogic practices when comparing to control group.

Key Words: Yogic Practices, College women, Vital Capacity, Spirometer.

Introduction:

The literal meaning of the word yoga is Yoke. It means for uniting the individual spirit with the universal spirit or God. The word yoga is derived from the roots of Sanskrit "YUJ" which means to join, to attach, to bind and yoke and to concentrate on one's attention. The science of yoga works on physical, mental, emotional, psychic and spiritual aspects of a person. When imbalance is experienced at this level, the organs, and muscles and nerves no longer function in harmony, rather they are in opposition to each other. Therefore yoga aims at bringing the different body functions into proper co-ordination so that they work for the good of the whole body. Yoga has a complete message for humanity. It is a message for the human body, human mind and human soul (Swami Kuvalayanana, 1977).

Methodology:

The purpose of the study was to find out the effect of yogic practices on selected physiological variables among college women. To achieve the purpose of this study thirty women were randomly selected from Government Sanskrit College, Thiruvananthapuram. The subject's age ranged between 18 to 21 years only. They were randomly divided into two equal groups, experimental group and control group. All the subjects were healthy and physically fit. The nature and importance of this study was explained to the subjects and subjects expressed their willingness to serve as subjects in this study. The study was formulated as a true random group design consisting of a pre test and post test. The subjects (N=30) were randomly assigned to two equal groups of fifteen students. The groups were assigned as experimental group, and control group respectively. Pretest was conducted for all the subjects on selected physiological variables. The experimental group participated yogic practices for a period of six weeks. The post test was conducted on the above said dependent variables after a period of six weeks in the respective treatments. The training programme was scheduled at 6.30 to 7.30 a.m on Monday, Wednesday and Friday. slow vital capacity, forced vital capacity was measured through spirometer. The data collected from the subjects were treated with statistical technique, the analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was used to find out the effects of yogic practices on selected physiological variables among college women.

Results and Discussion:

Table 1: Computation of Mean and Analysis of Covariance of Slow Vital Capacity of Experimental and Control Groups

	Experimental Group	Control Group	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F
Pre Test Mean	1.95	1.94	BG	0.001	1	0.001	0.06
			WG	0.418	28	0.01	
Post Test Mean	2.57	1.92	BG	3.14	1	3.14	57.01*
			WG	1.54	28	0.05	
Adjusted Post Mean	2.58	1.92	BG	3.19	1	3.19	60.05*
			WG	1.43	27	0.05	

* Significant at 0.05 level

The above table indicates the adjusted mean value of slow vital capacity of experimental and control groups were 2.58 and 1.92 respectively. The obtained F-ratio of 60.05 for adjusted mean was greater than the table value 4.21 for the degrees of freedom 1 and 27 required for significance at 0.05 level of confidence. The result of the study indicates that there was a in significant difference among experimental and control groups on slow vital capacity. The above table also indicates that both pre and post test means of experimental and control groups also differ significantly. The pre, post and Adjusted mean values of slow vital capacity of both control and experimental groups are graphically represented in the figure 1.

Figure 1: Bar Diagram Shows the Mean Value on Slow Vital Capacity of Experimental and Control Groups

Table 2: Computation of Mean and Analysis of Covariance of Forced Vital Capacity of Experimental and Control Groups

	Experimental Group	Control Group	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F
Pre Test Mean	1.94	1.96	BG	0.001	1	0.001	0.10
			WG	0.29	28	0.01	
Post Test Mean	2.49	1.96	BG	2.11	1	2.11	103.04*
			WG	0.57	28	0.02	
Adjusted Post Mean	2.49	1.96	BG	2.12	1	2.12	101.29*
			WG	0.56	27	0.02	

* Significant at 0.05 level

The above table indicates the adjusted mean value of forced vital capacity of experimental and control groups were 2.49 and 1.96 respectively. The obtained F-ratio of 101.29 for adjusted mean was greater than the table value 4.21 for the degrees of freedom 1 and 27 required for significance at 0.05 level of confidence. The result of the study indicates that there was a in significant difference among experimental and control groups on forced vital capacity. The above table also indicates that both pre and post test means of experimental and control groups also differ significantly. The pre, post and Adjusted mean values of forced vital capacity of both control and experimental groups are graphically represented in the figure 2.

Figure 2: Bar Diagram Shows of the Mean Value on Forced Vital Capacity of Experimental and Control Groups

Conclusion:

- It was concluded that there was significant improvement in slow vital capacity due to yogic practices when comparing to control group.
- It was concluded that there was significant improvement in forced vital capacity due to yogic practices when comparing to control group.

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